

1. Resource Title

Interview Methodology for the Study of the Use of the Body in Protest Contexts in South Korea and Chile during the 1980s.

2. Authors and Roles

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3. Description of the Content

This resource contains narrative interviews and written questionnaires conducted with participants in resistance movements in South Korea and Chile during the dictatorships of the 1980s. It was developed within the framework of a comparative qualitative research project focused on the study of the Body as a space of political, symbolic, and social resistance in both dictatorial contexts.

The methodology combines the analysis of bibliographic and historical sources with first-hand testimonies. Empirical data were obtained through one in-depth oral interview with a South Korean participant and two written questionnaires administered to Chilean participants, all based on a shared interview guide. The material was used for a qualitative and interpretive analysis of embodied experiences of resistance and repression.

4. Research Context

General objective

To analyse the condition of the Body as a phenomenon embedded within a plural space of resistance and political-symbolic enunciation in the dictatorial contexts of South Korea and Chile during the 1980s.

Specific objectives

- a) To comparatively describe forms of resistance in both dictatorships.
- b) To characterise the uses of the Body within these practices of resistance.
- c) To analyse the effects and consequences of such embodied practices in both contexts.

Conceptual Framework and Methodological Approach

The research adopts a qualitative approach of an interpretive and phenomenological nature, focused on the analysis of meaning, lived experience, and the symbolic dimension of the Body in contexts of political repression.

Methodology

The study combines the analysis of bibliographic sources (books, academic articles, and journalistic materials, mainly collected online) with testimonial material. Narrative interviews and written questionnaires were conducted with participants in resistance movements in South Korea and Chile during the 1980s.

An intentional (purposive) sampling strategy was applied, selecting individuals who had directly participated in experiences of resistance during the dictatorships. The testimonial corpus consists of one oral interview with a South Korean participant and two written questionnaires completed by Chilean participants. This methodological decision was adopted due to logistical difficulties in conducting online interviews, as the researcher was residing in South Korea during the fieldwork period.

The aim of working with social actors was to gain in-depth insight into subjectivities and perceptions of the Body as a space of sacrifice, repression, and resistance. In addition, a limited collection of photographic records of resistance movements in both countries was incorporated as complementary analytical material.

5. Type of Data

The data comply with the CESSDA standard.

Type of interviews: Narrative interviews based on a shared semi-structured questionnaire.

Number of cases: 1 oral interview (South Korean case) and 2 written questionnaires (Chilean cases).

Duration: The oral interview lasted approximately 2.5 hours; response time was not recorded for the written questionnaires.

Mode of recording:

South Korean interview: audio recording followed by verbatim transcription.

Chilean cases: written responses.

6. Methodological Procedure

Question Design Process:

The questions were developed on the basis of the research objectives, with the aim of exploring participants' embodied experiences during the Chilean dictatorship and the use of the body as a space of repression, resistance, and political action. Open-ended and reflective questions were chosen in order to enable the reconstruction of memories, perceptions, and meanings of the body from a subjective and situated perspective.

Sampling Protocol and Selection Criteria:

An intentional (purposive) sampling strategy was employed. Participants were selected on the basis of having lived through, directly or indirectly, the period of the Chilean dictatorship, or of possessing a well-developed reflection on the body, political violence, and resistance. Statistical representativeness was not sought; rather, the emphasis was placed on qualitative depth and experiential relevance.

Conditions of Implementation and Data Collection Mode:

Due to the researcher's residence in South Korea during the research period and the difficulties involved in coordinating online interviews with Chilean participants, a mixed methodological approach was adopted. Two written surveys were administered to Chilean participants, who responded in writing to the questionnaire. One in-depth interview was conducted with a South Korean participant in a synchronous format.

Interview / Questionnaire Guide:

The same set of questions was used for both the oral interview and the written questionnaires, ensuring thematic coherence across the different formats.

Transcription Process

The oral interview was audio-recorded and subsequently transcribed verbatim. The written questionnaires were directly incorporated into the analytical corpus.

Questionnaire

- 1) What is your name, age, and gender?
- 2) What does the body mean to you? (Please characterise the body in a way that challenges its use in resistance.)
- 3) How do you perceive your own body and the bodies present in public space?
- 4) In what ways do you recall the body being used or experienced during the Chilean dictatorship?
- 5) How do you remember or perceive your body in the context of demonstrations?
- 6) In what ways was the body used as a tool or object of struggle in protests?
- 7) What relationship do you think exists between the concepts of body, repression, and resistance in the context of the dictatorship?
- 8) What role do you feel suicides/self-immolations played as acts of resistance?
- 9) What does the word "martyr" evoke for you, and how do you see it as related to the body?

10) Do you believe that the use of the body in protests produced any favourable outcomes or was effective? Were there any effects achieved through the body that you experienced or remember?

11) Did your conception of the body change as a result of its use in contexts of resistance?

12) Do you believe there was a political-performative use of the body in resistance against the dictatorship?

7. Privacy, Ethics, and Consent Information

Written consent was obtained in the case of the written questionnaires. Participant anonymity was ensured through the use of pseudonyms and the removal of identifiable information. The data were used exclusively for academic and research purposes, with access restricted to the researcher.

Explicit permission was granted solely for use within the context of a master's thesis and one academic article. Full dissemination of the interview content is not authorised, at the explicit request of the participants.

8. Licence

Recommended licence: CC BY 4.0 (Open Science).

9. How to Cite This Methodology

APA format.